

USING PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN TEACHING HISTORY IN SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study provides information on the pedagogical foundations of using modern methods in teaching history in schools, and provides information on the introduction of modern teaching technologies in history. It also provides information on the development of teaching methods based on modern pedagogical approaches and innovative educational programs in accordance with modern educational curricula.

Introduction

The process of teaching history in schools is a complex pedagogical process that not only provides students with information about past events, but also helps them form their thinking, guide them to understand social processes, and help them mature as individuals. The content of history teaching is formed in accordance with the general goals of education and requires in-depth methodological preparation from the teacher. A history lesson should not be limited to memorizing a chain of facts, but should be aimed at forming the student as a person who can see the causes and consequences of events, has historical thinking, can reason based on evidence, and is responsible for his or her own point of view. Therefore, pedagogical methods in history are one of the most important components of the educational process, and their correct selection and effective application determine the quality of education. The main task of pedagogical methods in teaching history is to direct the student's activity, involve him in the process of knowledge and teach him to analyze. In order for students to understand the content of historical events more deeply, lessons should be built on the active participation of students. Working with historical texts, maps, sources, graphs and scientific literature activates the mental activity of students, helps them form historical thinking. In order to delve deeply into the content of past events, the teacher should avoid monotony in methods and build the lesson in a lively, logical, psychologically appropriate way for the student's age. In history lessons, methods such as storytelling, explanation, conversation, and working with sources have played a key role for many years. The narrative method serves as an important tool for explaining the sequence of historical events in an understandable way. The teacher's artistic, figurative story brings historical facts to life, and the life of the past is embodied in the imagination of students. The explanation method allows for a scientific interpretation of complex historical concepts, political processes, economic relations, and stages of cultural development. The conversation method encourages students to think actively, and through

questions their level of knowledge is determined and strengthened. The uniqueness of history is that it requires the study of events in an interconnected manner. Therefore, cause-and-effect relationships play a special role in historical thinking. Interactive methods are effective in understanding these relationships. For example, discussion methods teach students to analyze two or more points of view, compare them, and draw conclusions based on evidence. Issues such as the activities of historical figures, political relations between states, military decisions, and economic policy often require a multifaceted approach, not a one-sided explanation. Discussion methods are useful in such issues, forming social skills in students such as drawing logical conclusions, justifying their own opinions, and listening to the opinions of others. Methods such as brainstorming serve to develop various ideas, hypotheses, and solutions in students regarding the question or problem posed by the teacher. This method is especially effective in topics where there are different options for interpreting historical facts. Because a one-sided assessment of events in history does not always give the right result. The student must compare different points of view to understand the essence of the event. Working with sources is of particular importance in history. Since historical sources are direct witnesses to events, analyzing them forms a scientific approach in students. In the process of working with a source, the student extracts the main facts from the text, determines the author's position, and evaluates its role in creating a historical picture. This moves students from superficial memorization to scientific-analytical thinking. The development of modern technologies has created new opportunities for history lessons. Multimedia presentations, animations, virtual museums, 3D models, digital maps, online historical resources expand students' imagination. With the help of virtual tours, students feel as if they are seeing ancient cities, palaces, battlefields, and cultural monuments with their own eyes. Digital technologies allow us to see historical processes in space and time, which contributes to the meaningful assimilation of historical knowledge. A history teacher can make the lesson more interesting, lively, and effective using digital resources. For example, showing the changes in the territories of countries over time on interactive maps, graphically representing the life paths of historical figures, and analyzing the dynamics of economic processes through diagrams increases the quality and effectiveness of the lesson. Since students are of the current generation and quickly and easily perceive visual information, technologies are suitable for their learning process. Research-oriented education also plays an important role in history. Students learn independence, responsibility, curiosity, and creative thinking through activities such as mini-projects, practical research, studying historical sites, and analyzing archival documents. Research methods form the skills of creating a historical picture in students. Each student understands events through their own research during the project, which increases the personal value of knowledge for them. The assessment process in teaching history is also an important part of the methodological approach. Along with traditional assessment forms, competency-based assessment is carried out using various criteria. The student's activity, research, thinking, level of ability to work with sources, presentation skills, and historical analysis should also become an integral part of the assessment. To become a historical thinker, the student must not only remember facts, but also be able to think independently about them. The professional competence of a history teacher is a key factor in the teaching process. A teacher should not only know history well,

but also know how to teach it. Nowadays, it is natural that interest and attention to increasing the effectiveness of education using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process is growing day by day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at students finding their own knowledge, studying and analyzing it independently, and even drawing their own conclusions. The main reason why educational institutions today pay special attention to the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process can be explained as follows: The breadth of possibilities for implementing personal development education in pedagogical technologies in teaching history. Pedagogical technologies in history provide an opportunity to widely introduce a systematic approach to the educational process. Pedagogical technology in history encourages the teacher to design a technological chain in advance, starting from the goals of the educational process, to the establishment of a diagnostic system and monitoring the course of this process. The developing society itself has made a number of demands on social science teachers regarding in-depth teaching of history to students. A modern history teacher views education as a lifelong process. He should achieve the goal of forming historical consciousness and historical thinking in students, educating them in a sense of respect for the history and present day of the peoples of the world and our multinational people, their national and universal values, making students understand that the history of our statehood is an integral part of world civilization, and forming general and enhanced competencies in history for students. Educational conferences, scientific seminars, new methodological manuals, Internet resources, and international experience enrich the professional skills of the teacher. If the teacher regularly works on himself, modernity, creativity, and science will come into the lesson. There are several important aspects in improving history lessons. Lessons should be based on a combination of traditional and modern methods. Since the content of each topic is different, the teacher must show great pedagogical skill in choosing a method. While demonstration, game, and narrative methods are effective with younger students, methods such as working with sources, discussion, analyzing historical maps, and writing analytical essays give good results in higher grades. As a result, the history lesson becomes an educational field with interesting, analytical, lively, and scientific content for the student. The student begins to perceive history not as a museum exhibit of the past, but as the roots of present life. A deep understanding of the content of historical events awakens civic responsibility in them and forms a conscious approach to society. Correctly teaching history is one of the most effective ways to educate the future generation as conscious, knowledgeable, enlightened, and historically minded individuals. Components of the history teaching process and the relationships between them The regular relationships between the components of the history teaching process (goal, content, methods and techniques of teaching, results) are manifested as follows: just as the successful implementation of the goal and educational tasks in the secondary education and secondary specialized education system depends on the content of the teaching, its ideological, political and theoretical maturity, the level of students' mastery of the history course, in turn, depends on the extent to which they can appropriately use the forms of teaching, methods and techniques of teaching and tools that correspond to the purpose, educational tasks and content of the subject being studied. Also, the results of teaching depend on the teacher's ability to clearly define the intended goal of teaching, its

educational tasks, and to scientifically use methods and techniques that can help implement them in a manner consistent with the content of the course. As a result of this dialectical interrelationship between the components of the history teaching process, they continuously influence each other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that good results cannot be achieved in teaching history without relying on these laws and taking them into account. In order to direct education to a specific pedagogical goal, the teacher must clearly define the purpose of teaching history in the secondary education and secondary specialized education system, the educational and educational tasks that form its basis. At the same time, the role and tasks of the history course taught in each class in the implementation of general tasks, in turn, the specific tasks of each section in the implementation of the educational and educational tasks of teaching this course, the topics in the section, and even the topic covered in each lesson should be determined in advance. Because each history lesson has its place in the general system of lessons in the entire history course, this lesson solves some element or part of the general task set for teaching history in the secondary education and secondary specialized education system..

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